

Effects of E-Learning Modes on Undergraduate Students' Learning Outcomes in Mathematics among Distance Learning Institutions in Osun State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Mathematics, a major subject in science and indeed the secondary school level has witnessed deteriorating performances from students in their various external examinations. This phenomenon has attracted attention from all stakeholders in education, resulting in uncountable researches dealing on the curriculum and instructional strategies. Recently, the pervasive e-Learning instructional modes recorded tremendous successes in other subject areas, and may be applicable to mathematics at the secondary school level. This research therefore investigated the effects of two electronic-learning modes on the learning outcomes of undergraduates in distance learning institutions in Osun State, Nigeria. Quasi experimental design that employed pretest, post-test, control group design was adopted. Two null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 significance level. Mathematics Achievement Pre and Post-Tests with multiple choice questions and Mathematics Treatment Instruments were used to collect data from 600 Mathematics undergraduates that formed the sample of the study. A reliability coefficient above 0.80 was obtained for each of the research instruments using Cronbach's alpha coefficients. Analysis of Covariance together with Scheffe and Bonferroni post hoc techniques were used for the data analysis. The findings of the study showed that there were statistically significant differences in the performances of the three groups in favor of the two experimental groups. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that University lecturers should be encouraged to adopt e-Learning modes in their teaching so as to improve learning outcomes of students in mathematics.

Keywords: e-Learning, Video Based Learning, Virtual classroom and Effects

Introduction

Traditional face to face instructional strategy has been the popular mode of education in Nigeria, and it is teacher centered, engaging various methodologies such as lecture, demonstration, discussion, role play and brainstorming. In education, students learn and understand more quickly and easily from one another, but these facts are not taken into consideration in the conventional teaching technique (Umoh & Akpan, 2014). The system is not only boring, but condemned by many educationists for promoting rote learning. Thus, this conventional style alone can no longer be suitable for individual requirements and it is necessary to use modern technology as a supplement and to cater for individual differences in learning styles. Consequently, traditional face to face methodology is presently being massively augmented by Electronic Learning (e-Learning).

E-Learning is defined as the use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) to develop and deliver pedagogically considered content to learners in an ubiquitous, engaging and interactive learner-centered environment for distance education and fully on-line purposes. E-Learning takes care of the future of higher education in Nigeria. Futurists are in high demand, they have a set of skills and a basis for exploring trends and signals which suggest scenarios for the future (Alexander, 2020). Graham, (2013) opined that e-Learning involves mixing various event-based activities such as live e-Learning, self-paced learning, synchronous on-line conference and training or asynchronous self-paced learning. E-Learning modes could be synchronous, asynchronous or hybrid (synchronous & asynchronous). Synchronous methods such as Virtual Classroom, videoconferencing and webinars are the teaching styles where learners and instructors interact in real time from different physical locations. In asynchronous methods such as Video Based Learning, e-Mail, file transfer, blogs and discussion

boards, the interaction is out of real time at learners' own time, place and pace. Virtual Classroom (MOODLE software) and Video Based Learning (VBL, pre-recorded videos) have been chosen for the purpose of this research.

The use of electronic and on-line learning introduce creativity into the teaching and learning of Mathematics, Jiao, (2020) opined that with on-line learning, creativity is unleashed with passion, the subjects include Mathematics with creative collaboration and leveraging social media for social action. Additionally, responses from the administered questionnaires revealed that using e-Learning at the student's pace can increase the levels of understanding in Mathematics.

Mathematics as a subject is important to pursue careers in engineering, medicine and social science disciplines. The subject is so vast and useful, students develop a phobia for, hate and run away from it, thereby the performance is always below average with poor learning outcomes and mass failure in the secondary school certificate and institutional examinations. Mathematics is very vital even for our daily businesses and livelihood, there is virtually no area of human endeavor where it does not have application. The subject is compulsory in secondary school, whether the students are in science, commercial, arts or social science classes (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2014). Students intending to offer science and social science courses in the higher institutions require credit passes in Mathematics.

Despite the significant role of Mathematics in the educational system and our everyday lives, there has been a decline in the performances of students in the subject at the secondary school level. The statistics of West African Examination Council (WAEC) results on yearly basis reveal persistent poor performances of students in Mathematics. The poor performances of students in Mathematics in Nigeria have been attributed to many factors such as poor teaching facilities, inadequate equipment, lack of visual instructional materials, large numbers of students to teachers, Mathematics phobia and fright, poor teaching methods and lack of confidence in the subject. In addition, low self-concept and motivation, limited background preparation in Mathematics, lack of interest, poor government policies and poor problem-solving abilities. Others are teachers' inappropriate qualifications and training, students' environment, use of traditional chalk and talk method; students' attitudes, mental ability, gender and insufficient use of resources for teaching and learning (Okebukola, 2012).

The research also sought to establish a gender gap in the utilization of Virtual classroom mode in teaching Mathematics among Male and Female students in the area of study. Gender in the context here is the social and cultural roles assigned to the male or female sex. Daniel (2016), Liao (2013), Aderoju (2015) and Whitley (2017) in their various studies, found out that the attitudes towards technology vary significantly between male and female students. The assertion here is that males showed more interest, knowledge and positive attitudes and used it more often than their female counterparts. It is also observed that females view technology as more difficult and less interesting (Abiodun, 2017). However, the difference in attitudes between the two genders towards technology is not attributed to their biological nature but to their social and cultural construction.

Nevertheless, e-Learning modes can address some of the problems brought about by insufficient use of resources. Such learning resources comprise of books, audio-visual materials, flash cards, slides, filmstrips, film records, realia and multimedia. Devices include Telecommunication equipment, Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) such as computers, internet, well fixed line communications, mobile phones, scanners, CDs, DVDs, e- Mails, multimedia products that may be distributed on videotapes and global positioning systems (Ministry of Economic Development, 2014). The problem could also be solved by training Mathematics Distance Learning undergraduates who are the would-be-teachers of these students with the usage of e-Learning modes. As such upon graduation and while on the field, they will be able to inculcate e-Learning methodologies into the teaching and learning of Mathematics in order to improve the achievements and the attitudes of students.

Distance education or Open Distance Learning (ODL) for students who may not always be physically present in a school, evolved in response to the need to provide educational access to learners who would not be able to participate in face-to-face access because they have grown past school age, they are working or for religious reasons. It offers a flexible, cost-effective way to improve academic skills and employment prospects (Shelly & Holliman, 2017). Single mode distance learning institutions are the ones where teaching and learning are designed to provide for distance education only, the mode is completely committed to delivering and achieving high quality professional standards in ODL. Dual mode distance learning institutions are those where teaching and learning support both campus based and distance education, they are advantageously characterized by offering on campus and distance education courses that meet the same quality and standard.

Based on the above literature, the present study investigated the effects of two e-Learning modes on the learning outcomes of Mathematics undergraduates in single and dual mode distance learning institutions in Osun State, Nigeria.

The quest for raising the quality of education in Nigeria has been on the rise. Many research findings have shown that students learn Mathematics best when they are actively engaged in learning and participate in the learning process in an interactive, learner-centered manner such as are provided by e-Learning modes. In the Nigerian higher education context, there has been a rapid change in the role of the lecturer in recent years, lecturers face many new changes and challenges and they are

required to adapt to such. Included in these are more western and modernized approaches to the impartation of knowledge, new methods of teaching and learning and most importantly an explosion in the development of teaching distance learners within the e-Learning environment. E-learning is a key component of the system and organizational level changes needed to effectively implement on-line learning as a strategy (Nichols, 2020). These imply that teachers, facilitators and lecturers need to update their knowledge and skills to develop the educational process either in the classroom (Ogunleye & Ojo, 2019) or on-line (Ogunleye & Apata, 2018). With on-line learning, it becomes imperative for the academic staff to produce versions of their campus courses for distance students and interact with them by e-Mail and other web tools. Dede, (2020) averred that there is the need to think strategically about lifelong learning while universities need to think whether their current programs and modes of operation need to be re-imagined and re-designed.

The advent and a new philosophy towards e-Learning, its role in education and a wide range of researchers have developed the desired investigation of the role of e-Learning and its translation into an interactive educational environment. Many studies have provided evidence on the significant contributions that e-Learning makes to improving methods of teaching and positively impacting the learner (Kennewell, 2017). However, such studies have been limited to investigating the impact of e-Learning on learners. There is substantially less research focusing on the role which e-Learning plays in creating and promoting a more interactive educational environment as part of teaching and learning with improvement on the learning outcomes of learners in single and dual mode distance learning institutions. The use of e-Learning to create interactive educational environments can help to develop thinking skills and transform classrooms to environments affording rapid educational growth. Using e-Learning to teach also helps the student to develop new thinking skills which may transfer to different situations that require analysis and comprehension skills, and consequently critical skill development (Cooperman, 2017).

The investigation of the effects of e-Learning modes on undergraduate students' learning outcomes in Mathematics among distance learning institutions was carried out in Osun State, Nigeria. The two e-Learning modes investigated were synchronous Virtual Classroom using MOODLE software and asynchronous Video Based Learning (VBL) using pre-recorded videos. They were used to research the teaching of Mathematics among male and female undergraduate distance learners in comparison with traditional classroom methods. This was in reaction to the contradicting research reports on the effectiveness of e-Learning and in an effort to convert the interest of today's students in electronic gadgets to foster the educational standard and enhance job opportunities.

This study determined the effects of these widely growing e-Learning techniques on distance learning in general and specifically on the distance learners' achievements. The moderating effects of gender on students' learning outcomes in Mathematics using the two e-Learning modes was also determined.

Objectives of the study

The purpose of this study was to determine the effects of Electronic Learning modes of Virtual Classroom and Video Based Learning on the learning outcomes of Mathematics undergraduates in distance learning institutions in Osun State, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to determine the:

1. Effects of using the two e-Learning modes of Virtual Classroom and Video Based Learning, and conventional Lecture method on Mathematics undergraduates' learning outcomes in distance learning institutions in Osun State, Nigeria.
2. Effects of using the two e-Learning modes of Virtual Classroom and Video Based Learning, and conventional Lecture method on male and female Mathematics undergraduates' learning outcomes in distance learning institutions in Osun State, Nigeria.

Research Questions:

The two research questions raised for the study were:

1. What are the effects of using the two e-Learning modes of Virtual Classroom and Video Based Learning, and conventional Lecture method on Mathematics undergraduates' learning outcomes in distance learning institutions in Osun State, Nigeria?
2. What are the effects of using the two e-Learning modes of Virtual Classroom and Video Based Learning, and conventional Lecture method on male and female Mathematics undergraduates' learning outcomes in distance learning institutions in Osun State, Nigeria?

Hypotheses:

Based on the stated problem, the following two null research hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. There is no significant difference between the learning outcomes of Mathematics undergraduates exposed to the two e-Learning modes of Virtual Classroom and Video Based Learning, and those taught with conventional Lecture method in distance learning institutions in Osun State, Nigeria.
2. There is no significant difference between the learning outcomes of male and female Mathematics undergraduates exposed to the two e-Learning modes of Virtual Classroom and Video Based Learning, and those taught with conventional Lecture methods in distance learning institutions in Osun State Nigeria.

Methodology

The research design employed for this research was non randomized quasi experimental design using pretest, post-test and control group design. This involved three groups comprising two levels of experiment and one control group, i.e. Experimental group 1-Virtual Classroom, Experimental group 2-Video Based Learning and conventional lecture method as control group. The independent variables were the three teaching methods, these are (i) Virtual Classroom using MOODLE software (ii) Video Based Learning using prerecorded videos and (iii) Lecture method. The dependent variable was the Mathematics undergraduates' learning outcomes in the three groups while the moderating variable was gender of students in the study. Pretest was administered to test the initial knowledge of the participants before their exposure to the teaching modes in three groups. After 6 weeks of treatment, the post test was administered on the three groups together to determine the various effects of the teaching modes on participants

The population comprised all distance learning University undergraduates in Nigeria. The target population were distance learning undergraduate students from two Universities in Osun State and it involved all 100 level Mathematics undergraduates of the two institutions.

Stratified and purposive sampling techniques were adopted for the study. The selection of samples was purposive relying on the researcher's judgment and based on following criteria: They: (1) offer Mathematics courses and are computer literate (2) owned computer systems in the form of laptops, i-Pads, computer tablets or android phones (3) were 100 level undergraduates. Specifically focusing the first semester 100 level course coded MTH/MATH 111 with course titles Algebra and Elementary Mathematics in the 2021/22 academic session. 300 male and 300 female students were selected and systematically assigned to their treatment groups, 240 undergraduates were exposed to each of the two e-Learning modes of Virtual Classroom and Video Based Learning as Experimental groups 1 and 2 respectively while 120 of them were taught using conventional lecture method as the Control group.

The instruments used for this research were the Mathematics Achievement Pre-Test (MAP), Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT), and the Mathematics Treatment Instrument (MTI). The MAP was a test instrument consisting of 50 Mathematics multiple choice questions. It was used to elicit the entry knowledge of the subjects to the study and conducted for the two experimental groups and the control group. The contents were the mathematics topics covered in the treatment instrument with the exception of complex numbers which is not expected to be part of their previous knowledge as the topic is not included in the secondary school certificate syllabus. The questions were drawn on the various topics as specified in a test blueprint. The MTI was the treatment instrument and was based on the course MTH 111 (or MAT/MA/ MATH 111) as being offered by the various institutions in the State following a detailed analysis of the curricula. This was used to expose the students to the three modes of teaching which were Virtual Classroom (MOODLE software for Experimental group I), Video Based Learning (prerecorded video for Experimental group 2) and traditional face to face teaching method (Control group). The content of the instrument was prepared based on selected topics which are common to the institutions' course contents on the particular course. Each of the 6 units consisted of the instructional and behavioral objectives for each of the teaching modes and the materials for presentation. The units were also divided into subtitled frames for easy coverage by the researcher as the presenter for experimental group 1 (Virtual Classroom) and the Control group (face to face lecture) as well as for the students' easy self-study for those in experimental group 2 (Video Based Learning). The 6 topics covered were in 3 modules, each module consisted of 2 units. Module 1-Unit 1: Arithmetic and Geometric progression, Unit 2: Set Theory; Module 11-Unit 1: Linear and Quadratic equations, Unit 2: Differentiation and Integration; Module 3-Unit 1: Vectors and Unit 2: Complex numbers. The instrument was prepared with many solved examples in each unit with exercises which consisted of many practice questions with answers and marks appropriately at the end of each topic, this was used by the students for self-study and to test their levels of understanding at each stage. The entire instrument was based on the six levels of cognitive domains of Remembering, Understanding, Applying, Analyzing, Evaluating and Creating.

The MAT was used as a post-test. The questions were based on the topics and contents of the treatment instrument. It was slightly different from the pretest but was similarly administered to both the experimental and control groups. MAT

consisted of 50 multiple choice questions constructed using a table of specification/test blueprint as classified by Krathwohl & Anderson in the revised Bloom's Taxonomy (2001).

The research instruments were presented to two experts each in the Mathematics and Educational Technology departments for proper scrutiny, content and construct validity. The items were matched with the table of specification. The treatment instrument was also matched with selected topics. Based on the experts' suggestions and criticisms, the researchers modified some of the items. Revision and corrections were adequately made as necessary. The reliability of the research instruments was established by a trial run with 40 Mathematics undergraduates from the population outside the study group using test-retest method in an interval of two weeks. A correlation coefficient of 0.80 was obtained using Cronbach's Alpha Coefficients for each of the test instruments.

The researchers first solicited for the cooperation of the students through the heads of Mathematics and Education departments as applicable to the researched institutions. The two test instruments for data collection in this research which were the pretest and posttest were administered in stages at each of the institutions. The first sets of data collected were from the pre tests conducted in the first week of the study, the stratification of students to male and female was done in the first week. The scores were systematically used to allocate the experimental subjects to treatment in the three stated groups. Group 1 (Virtual Classroom Group) was taught using MOODLE software subjecting them to synchronous teaching, problem solving interactions of questions and answers sessions. The researchers also uploaded the teaching material with relevant videos for each topic to the MOODLE site and thereafter sent the link to the MOODLE software site and the log in details which consisted of the user name and password for each person. They then copied files to their own pages, attended lectures, did assignments and assessed their own work through the grade book. They also synchronously interacted with the researchers in real time thus enabling their further understanding of the topics. Group 2 (Video Based Learning group) received prerecorded videos of the same teaching material on-line and on compact disks. This consisted of six teaching sessions produced by the researchers and supplied one per institution, it subjected the students to asynchronous teaching in their own time, they then sent their questions by e-Mail to the researchers who mailed the solutions back to them. This enabled their self-study in their own time. Group 3 (Traditional classroom group) was taught by traditional face to face lecture method also using the same treatment instrument. They had direct contact and interactions with the researcher which enabled them to ask questions and receive instant answers. The instruction of students lasted for 6 weeks (the 2nd to 7th week) at a session of one hour per week, covering one unit of the six-unit treatment instruments per week. The samples from each institution were taught using the treatment instruments prepared by the researchers. After this, the post-tests were conducted whereby the Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) was administered in each institution and used to collect the second sets of data, this lasted for one week.

The pretest was administered to the three groups at the beginning of the experiment using Mathematics Achievement Pre-Test (MAP), while post-test using MAT was administered after 6 weeks to measure their performances. Data from the pretest and post-test were subjected to data analysis. Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was chosen to analyze the data which were the pretest and post-test scores, using the pretest scores as covariates. Where the main effects were found significant, Scheffe and Bonferroni Post Hoc tests were used to trace the sources of such effects. The two hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The mean gain scores were graphically illustrated to distinctly show and compare the gains as score differences for each of the three modes used for teaching during the quasi-experimental study.

Results

Research Question 1

What are the effects of using the two e-Learning modes of Virtual Classroom and Video Based Learning, and conventional Lecture method on Mathematics undergraduates' learning outcomes in distance learning institutions in Osun State, Nigeria?

Table 1.1: Pre-test and post-test achievement scores of students taught using Virtual Classroom, Video Based learning and Lecture method in distance learning institutions

SN	Mode	N	Pretest Mean	Std. Deviation	Posttest Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Gain	Decision
1.	Virtual Classroom	240	53.84	9.04	70.63	7.57	16.79	1 st

2.	Video Based Learning	240	53.50	8.92	64.93	7.39	11.43	2 nd
3.	Conventional	120	58.59	8.39	59.35	7.99	0.96	3 rd

Table 1 shows the pre and post-test scores with the mean gains for each of the learning groups. The mean gains therefore placed Virtual Classroom ahead of the Video Based Learning and the control group in the distance learning students. This is revealed in Figure 1.

Research Question 2

What are the effects of using the two e-Learning modes of Virtual Classroom and Video Based Learning, and conventional Lecture method on male and female Mathematics undergraduates' learning outcomes in distance learning institutions in Osun State, Nigeria?

Table 1.2: Pretest and Post-test Mathematics Achievements of Male and Female Distance Learning Students

SN	Gender	N	Pretest Mean	SD	Posttest Mean	SD	Mean Gain	Decision
1.	Male	300	55.32	9.44	67.14	8.46	11.82	1 st
2.	Female	300	53.90	8.60	65.05	8.77	11.15	2 nd

Table 2 shows that male students had a pretest mean score of 55.32 with a post-test mean score of 67.14. The mean gain of 11.82 was obtained by the group. Trailing the males are their female counterparts who obtained 53.90 at pretest and 65.05 at post-test to record an 11.15 mean gain which is lower than the record of the male students.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the learning outcomes of Mathematics undergraduates exposed to the two e-Learning modes of Virtual Classroom and Video Based Learning, and those taught with conventional Lecture methods in distance learning institutions in Osun State, Nigeria.

Figure 1: Graphical Illustration of Learning Outcomes and Mean Gain Scores of Virtual Classroom, Video Based Learning and Traditional Teaching Methods

Table 2: ANCOVA Results of the Scores of Students Taught Using Virtual Classroom, Video Based Learning and Traditional Teaching Method

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P-Value
Corrected Intercept	365.239	3	121.746	40.240	0.000
Model	505.585	1	505.585	167.107	0.000
Main effect(treatment)	51.485	2	25.742	8.508*	0.000
Pretest	131.440	1	131.440	43.444	0.000
Error	245.067	81	3.026		
Total	25585.000	61			
Corrected Total	610.306	60			

*Significant at 0.05

To test H_{01} , ANCOVA and Scheffe post-hoc tests were carried out as shown in Tables 2, 3 and 4.1. As illustrated in Table 2, there was a significant main effect of learning strategy on students' performances, $F(1, 81), p < 0.05$. The results revealed that there were significant differences in the performances of Virtual Classroom, Video Based Learning and control groups taught Mathematics. Hence,

Hypothesis one (H₀₁) was rejected.

In order to establish the difference among the three groups, Scheffe post-hoc analysis was conducted as shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Summary of Scheffe Analysis of Significant Difference on Mean Performance Scores of Undergraduates in the Three Groups

S/N	Variable (i)	Variable (j)	Mean Difference (i-j)	P-Value
1.	Virtual	Virtual	1.1333	0.129
	Classroom	Traditional	4.0533	0.000*
2.	VBL	VBL	-1.1333	0.129
		Traditional	2.9200	0.000*
3.	Traditional Method	Virtual	-4.0533	0.000*
		VBL	-2.9200	0.000*

*: Significant
at 0.05 alpha
level

Table 3 revealed that there was no significant difference between students taught using Virtual Classroom and Video Based Learning ($P > 0.05$). Furthermore, there was a significant difference between undergraduates taught using Virtual Classroom and Traditional method ($P < 0.05$). Similarly, there was a significant difference between undergraduates exposed to Video Based Learning and those taught with Traditional methods.

Table 4.1: Mean Performance Scores of Undergraduates Taught Using Virtual Classroom, Video Based Learning (VBL) and Traditional Lecture Method

SN	Mode	N	Pretest	Posttest	Mean Gain
			Mean	Mean	Score
1.	Virtual Classroom	240	12.77	18.73	5.96
2.	Video Based Learning	240	11.67	17.60	5.93
3.	Traditional Lecture	120	9.12	14.60	5.56

Table 4.1 shows that there was improvement in the post-test scores of the three groups but both the Virtual Classroom and Video Based Learning groups had higher mean gains than the lecture group. The Virtual Classroom group had a mean gain score of 5.96, followed by Video Based learning group with a mean gain score of 5.93, and Traditional lecture method group had a mean gain score of 5.56. This was further illustrated in Figure 1.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between the learning outcomes of male and female Mathematics undergraduates exposed to the two e-Learning modes of Virtual Classroom and Video Based Learning, and those taught with conventional Lecture methods in distance learning institutions in Osun State Nigeria.

Table 4.2 Male and Female Undergraduates' Post-test Mathematics Achievements

SN	Gender	N	Standard	Confidence Interval (95%)		
			Mean Score	Error Margin	Lowest Bound	Uppermost Bound
1.	Male	300	65.79	0.51	64.79	66.79
2.	Female	300	64.47	0.48	63.52	65.42

Table 4.2 shows that male participants achieved better in posttest Mathematics score (mean=65.79) than their female counterparts (mean=64.47). This difference has been proved to be marginal as the ANCOVA test was not significant. Thus **Hypothesis 2 (H₀₂) was rejected.**

The study revealed that Mathematics undergraduates exposed to the two e-Learning modes of instruction which were Virtual Classroom and Video Based Learning performed better than those taught by lecture method in distance learning institutions in Osun State (Figure 1). In addition:

1. Gender has no effect whatsoever on the performances of the undergraduates.
2. There was improvement of the post test scores in the three groups but students in the two experimental groups that were exposed to e-Learning modes both had higher gains than those in the group taught with Traditional classroom methods. This was revealed as shown in Figure 1 and Table 4.1, the mean gain score of students in the Virtual Classroom group was highest (5.96) followed by the Video Based Learning group (5.93) and the least was the Traditional classroom group (5.56). This shows that the distance learning undergraduates recorded better learning outcomes with the use of e-Learning modes for the teaching of Mathematics.
3. E-Learning is an effective mode of instruction that can be used to reduce the failure rate in Mathematics in the West African School Certificate Examination (WASCE) results.

Discussion of Findings

This study used MOODLE software and prerecorded video recordings as experimental instructional strategies and traditional lecture method as control for the teaching and learning of Mathematics in distance learning institutions in Osun State, Nigeria. The findings are in agreement with that of Clement, (2015) who opined that e-Learning is a promising alternative learning approach that can improve student's success, satisfaction and performance. It also agrees with Al-Qahtani & Higgins, (2013), Giovengo, (2014) and Sisco, Woodcock, & Eady, (2015) who all reported significant differences among e-Learning and traditional teaching methods in favor of e-Learning. The findings however contradict that of Okon & Akpara, (2014) who reported non availability, non-acceptability and inadequate ICT skills as barriers towards the utilization of e-Learning tools. Also contrary to the reports of Chang, Shu, Liang, Tseng, & Hsu, (2014) who reported no significant difference in the achievements of students exposed to e-Learning and Traditional teaching methods.

The superiority of e-Learning over traditional face to face methods as seen in this study stems from the fact that e-Learning engages the cognitive, affective and psychomotor aspects of learning for better understanding and performance. This finding further goes to support the perspectives of Clement, (2015). The outstanding performances of students exposed to Virtual Classroom and Video Based Learning over those taught with traditional methods confirmed that using e-Learning modes is a better approach of teaching Mathematics to distance learners in Osun State, Nigeria. The result is shown in Figure 1 and Table 4.1, this further negates the report of Okon & Akpara, (2014) who had negative reports. e-Learning modes are as such effective and efficient in the teaching and learning of Mathematics.

Conclusion

This study explored the effectiveness of e-Learning instructional modes on undergraduate performances at distance learning institutions in Osun State, Nigeria. The two e-Learning modes which are Virtual Classroom by the use of MOODLE software and Video Based Learning using prerecorded videos were found effective for learning Mathematics. The undergraduates taught with e-Learning performed better than their counterparts taught with traditional lecture methods. However, no statistically significant differences were found between the performances of male and female undergraduates exposed to the two e-Learning modes. This means e-Learning can bridge the gap between gender disparities in academic performance. Thus, the study has been able to show that e-Learning can be effectively used to teach Mathematics to improve the persistently woeful results of students in their West African School Certificate Examinations (WASCE). The undergraduates exposed to the two e-Learning modes are the would-be-teachers of the secondary school students, they will be able to use the experience gained to impart the acquired knowledge to the students for better results.

Recommendations

Sequel to the findings of this research, the following recommendations are made -:

1. The teaching process in Nigerian Universities should not rely on traditional lecture methods alone in relation to Mathematics. Other instructional strategies using e-Learning modes such as Virtual Classroom and Video Based Learning should be adopted to teach the subject in order to equip the would-be Mathematics teachers. This renders the teaching and learning process more flexible in terms of time and place.

2. E-Learning modes should also be used at the secondary school level to improve the poor performances consistently recorded in the West African School Certificate Examinations (WASCE). Mathematics teachers should expose students to e-Learning to promote student centered instructional approach, autonomy and self-discovery learning.
3. The Mathematics lecturers and teachers should be motivated, encouraged and reinforced with the skills of developing, producing and using electronic modes of teaching such as MOODLE software and Video Based recordings. This should not be seen as a substitute for the traditional method but supplementary modes of teaching and learning Mathematics in distance learning institutions in Nigeria.
4. Secondary school Mathematics curriculum should be reviewed with the intention of provision of interactive and technologically based instruction in the form of e-Learning modes in government and proprietary schools. Video and Audio CDs should not only be seen as being meant for social purposes alone or listening to music for pleasure but should be used for academic purposes.
5. ICT training should be conducted for Mathematics lecturers and teachers from time to time to update and get them acquainted with the latest technological innovations on e-Learning modes of instructions. This will enable them to develop, modify and maintain the latest on-line technologies within the schools and Universities.
6. Students should endeavor to explore the opportunities offered by e-Learning as it could be utilized to complement and supplement the conventional face to face method of teaching and learning as well as the individualized learning process.

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References

- Alden, J. (2015). Use of wikis to support collaboration amongst on-line students. In Yang, H. & Yuen, S. collective intelligence and e-learning: Implications of web-based Communities and networking. New York, NY: IGI Global.
- Al-Qahtani, A. A.Y. & Higgins, S.E. (2013). Effects of traditional, blended and e-Learning on students' achievements in higher education. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning* vol.29 (3), pages 220-234.
- Arkorful, V.; & Abaidoo, N. (2015). The role of e-Learning, advantages and disadvantages of its adoption in higher education. *International Journal of Instructional technology and Distance Learning* vol. 12 (1) pages 29-42.
- Aanditvilai, C. (2016). Enhancing students' language skills through blended learning. *Electronic Journal of e-Learning* vol. 14 (3), pages 220-229.
- Belleflame, P. & Jacqmin, J. (2014). An economic appraisal of Massive Open On-line Course-MOOC platforms: Business models And Impacts on Higher Education. CORE discussion Paper, Centre for operations, Research and Econometrics.
- Chang, V., Shu, Liang, Tseng, & Hsu, (2014). Is blended e-Learning better than traditional lassroom learning for vocational high school students? *Journal of Educational Technology* vol. 15 (2), pages 142-146.
- Chang, V. (2016). Review and discussion: e-Learning for academia and industry. *International Journal of Information Management* vol. (36) 3 pages 476-485.
- Cooperman, L. (2017). *The art of teaching on-line: How to start and how to succeed as an on-line instructor* Netherlands, Chandos.
- Costa, K. & Pancansky-Brock, M. (2020). 99 tips for creating simple and sustainable educational videos: A guide for on-line teachers and flipped classes. Sterling, Stylus Publishing.
- Daniela, L. (2020). *Pedagogies of digital learning in higher education*. London, Routledge.
- Daniels, E. (2015). *Creating motivating learning environments: What we can learn from Researchers and students*. Retrieved from <http://www.academia.edu/504/teachers>.
- David, A. S. & Schwaninger, A. (2021). Technology acceptance of four digital learning technologies (classroom response system, classroom chat, e-lectures and mobile reality) at 3 months usage. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education* vol.18 article no. 8 (2021).
- Dede, C.J. & Richards, J. (2020). *The 60- year curriculum - New models for lifelong learning in digital economy*. London, Routledge.

- Egbonwon, S. E., Adeyanju, L. J. & Salawu, I. O. (2012). EDT 801-Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in education. Lagos: National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN).
- Elmer, S.J., Carter, K. R., Armga, A.J. & Carter, J.R. (2016). Blended learning within an undergraduate exercise physiology laboratory. *Advances in Physiology Education Journal* vol. 40(1), pages 64-69.
- Ferriman, N. (2013). The impact of blended e-Learning on undergraduate academic essay writing in English (L2). *Journal of Computer and Education* vol. 60(1), pages 243-253.
- Frick, T. W., Myers, R. D., Dagli, C. & Berret, A. F. (2020). *Innovative learning analysis for evaluating instruction*. London: Routledge.
- Ganiyu, A. B., Okonkwo, C. A. & Nduka, O. (2012). *EDU 921-Advanced Educational research Methods*. Lagos, National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN).
- Gambari, A.I., Shittu, A.T., Ogunlade, O.O. & Osunlade, O.R. (2017). Effectiveness of Blended Learning modes of instruction on the performance of undergraduates in Kwara State, Nigeria. *Malaysian On-line Journal of Educational Sciences* vol. 5(1), Pages 25-36.
- Hathaway, D. Norton, P. (2018). *Understanding problems of practice: A case study in design research*, Springer briefs in educational communications and technology. Cham, Switzerland. Springer International Publishing.
- Hiralaal, A. (2012). Students' experiences of blended learning in accounting education at Durban University of Technology. *South African Journal of Higher Education* vol. 26(2), pages 316-328.
- Jensen, L. & Konradsen, F. (2018). A review of the use of virtual reality head mounted displays in education and training. *Education and Information Technologies Journal* 23 Vol.4, pages 1515-1529 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s/0639-017-9676-0>
- Jiao, H. & Lissitz, R. (2020). *Applications of artificial intelligence to assessment*. Charlotte NC, Information age publishing.
- Johnson, I. D. (2021). *The Willey handbook of collaborative on-line learning and global engagement*. New York: John Wiley & Sons Publishing.
- Kelly, K., Zakrajsek, T.D. & Pacansky-Brock, M. (2021). *Advancing on-line teaching: Creating equity-based digital learning environments*. Sterling P.V., Stylus Publishing.
- Kergel, D. (2020). *Digital learning in motion: From book culture to digital age*. London, Routledge.
- Kosslyn, S.M. (2020). *Active learning on-line: Five principles that make on-line course come alive* Copenhagen, Denmark. Alinea learning Publishing.
- Lancaster, A. (2019). *Driving performance through learning: Develop employees through effective workplace learning*. London, Kogan Place.
- Lee, C., Yeh, D., Kung, R. & Hsu, C. (2017). The influences of learning portfolios and attitudes on learning effects on blended e-Learning for Mathematics. *Journal of Educational Computing and Research*.
- Lowenthal, P.R. & Dennen, V.P. (2020), *Social presence and identity in on-line learning*. New York, Routledge.
- Mainoma, H.M. (2018). Information and Communication Technology in higher education and sustainable development. *East African Journal of Educational Research and Policy (EAJERP)*, vol. 13, pages 51-63. Published by Higher Educational Research and Policy Network (HERPNET).
- Newton, A.J. (2021). *Start a successful career today in Information Technology*. Independent Publishing network, Seven folks, United Kingdom
- Nwaboku, N. C., Eko, M. M., Sanni, I.O., Oluderu, I., Akindoju, O. G., Abolade, A. O. & Salawu, I.O. (2012). EDT 841-Conceptualization of instructional strategies. Lagos: National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN).
- Ogunleye, B. O. & Apata, F. S. (2018). Integrating intelligent pedagogical agents into learning management systems for student exposure to science experiments in the National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN). *KIU Journal of Education*, 13 (2), 31-51.
- Ogunleye, B. O. & Ojo, O. R. (2019). Impact of physical fitness activities on students' Basic Science achievement in selected Nigerian secondary schools. *Annual Journal of the Technical University of Varna, Bulgaria*, 3 (2), 21-31. ISSN 2603-316X (on-line): <https://doi.org/10.29114/ajtuv.vol3.iss2.145>.
- Oliver, J. (2021). *Self-directed multimodal learning in higher education*. Cape town, S.A. AOSIS Publishing.
- Omoifo, C. N., Badmus, G. A. & Okonkwo, C. A. (2012). *EDU 932: Advanced Educational Statistics*. Abuja, National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN) Press.
- Pachter, M. & Maier, B. (2012). Students' expectations of and experiences in E- learning: Their Relations to learning achievements and course satisfaction. *Journal of computer Education* available at <http://www.doc.doi.org/computer.educ>.
- Poritz, J.A. & Rees, J. (2017). *Education is not an App.: The future of University teaching in the internet age*. London, Routledge.

- Radianti, J., Majchrzak, T. A., Fromm, J. & Wohlgenannt, I. (2020). A systematic review of Immersive virtual reality applications for higher education: Design elements, lessons learned and research agenda. *Computer and Education Journal*, vol.147 page 103.
- Reich, J. (2015). Rebooting MOOC research. *Science Journal* vol. 347(6217), pages 34-35.
- Rodrigues, H., Almeida, F., Figueiredo, V. & Lopes, S. L (2019). Tracking e-Learning through published papers: A systematic review. *Computer Education Journal*, vol. 136 pages 87-98.
- Serravallo, J. (2020). *Connecting with students on-line: Strategies for remote teaching and learning*. Portsmouth, New Hampshire, Heinemann Publishing.
- Sisco, A., Woodcock, S. & Eady, M. (2015). Pre-service perspective on e-teaching: Assessing e- teaching using the EPEC hierarchy of conditions for e-Learning/teaching competence. *Canadian Journal of Learning and Technology* vol. 41(3).
- Umeh, V. O. & Umeh, C. D. (2012). The importance of Science, Technology and Mathematics Instruction (STMI) in achieving national unity. *Eastern COEASU journal of teacher Education-An official publication of the Colleges of Education academic staff union*.
- Umoh, J.B. & Akpan, E.T. (2014). Challenges of blended e-Learning tools in Mathematics: students' perspectives, University of Uyo. *Journal of Education and Learning* vol. 3(4) Pages 60-70
- Vallis, J. M., Mason, A. C., Afani-Dekyi, K., Anzotinge, E., Anwi, J., Chifwaila, L., Fraser, F., Moyo, P., Mudenda, C. & Turner, C. (2012). Building capacity for E-learning: Appropriate Computer techniques. *International conference paper*.
- Wang, S. (2011). Benefits and challenges of E-learning: University students' perspectives. Retrieved January 2020 from :<http://www.igi.global.com/chapter/benefits-challenges-learning>.
- Xu, J. & Quaddus, M. (2015). A six stage model for the effective diffusion of knowledge Management systems. *Journal of management development*.
- Yam, S. & Rossini, P. (2011). On-line learning and blended learning: Which is more effective? 17th Raccif Rim real estate society conference.